

ISSN: 2456-5474

RNI No. UPBIL/2016/68367

VOL.- X , ISSUE- IV May - 2025
Innovation The Research Concept

Study of a Piscian Cestode, *Mystoides ragauliensis* N.Sp. From *Heteropneustes fossilis* (Bloch.) From Ragauli, District Jalaun (U.P.) India

Paper Id : 20229 Submission Date : 2025-05-06 Acceptance Date : 2025-05-20 Publication Date : 2025-05-25
This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.16564703

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/innovation.php#8>

Alok Pathak
Assistant Professor
Zoology
D.V. College
Orai, Uttar Pradesh, India

Abstract

Three fishes, *Heteropneustes fossilis* (Bloch.) were examined at Ragauli, District-Jalaun (U.P.) India. One was found infected with single cestode in it's intestine.

After morphological study of the worm we reached on the conclusion that present species differs from known species of genus *Mystoides* in the worm, scolex, cirrus pouch, ovary, vitellaria, excretory tube-size, scolex shape, neck, testes postion, external- internal seminal vesicle, receptaculum seminis, genital pore and eggs.

Keywords *Heteropneustes fossilis* (Bloch), Jalaun Ragauli

Introduction

During the course of investigation of piscian tape worm three fishes *Heteropneustes fossilis* (Bloch.) were examined from Ragauli, District Jalaun (U.P.) one of them harboured single cestode in their intestine. Morphological studies of the cestode revealed to belong to a new species of the genus *Mystoides* of the family Capingentidae of order Caryophyllidea.

Objective of study

Study of a piscian cestode, *Mystoides ragauliensis* new species from *Heteropneustes fossilis* (Bloch.) from Ragauli, District-Jalaun (U.P.) India.

Review of Literature

A.K. Srivastav, A.R. Singh, Aditya Narayan (2011), Noopur Mathur, A.K. Srivastav, Aditya Narayan (2014) and Aditya Narayan, Dharendra Singh (2017) studied different species of genus *Mystodies* in Bundelkhand regions.

After morphological study of the worm we reached on the conclusion that present species (*Mystoides ragauliensis*) differs from known species of genus *Mystodies* in the scolex shape, neck length and testes position etc.

Main Text

- Fig. 1 - Scolex with neck (5X10)
- Fig. 2 - Middle region of the body (5X10)
- Fig. 3 - Posterior region of the body (5X10)
- Fig. 4 - Eggs (5X45)

S.N.	Character	<i>Mystoides rajwaranesis</i>	<i>Mystoides bundelkhandensis</i>	<i>Mystoides Chhaviensis</i>	<i>Mystoidesragauliensis n.sp.</i>
01	Size	18.0 – 30.0 × 0.53-1.55	37.2 × 1.6	20.140×22.541× 0.864 – 0.964	34.0× 1.484
02	Scolex Size Shape	0.557 – 0.662 × 0.413- 0.45 Spoon like without groove	1.60 × 0.57 Tube like without groove	0.565–0.812 × 0.208 – 0.279 Fimbricated with two grooves	0.970× 0.628 Thumb like without groove
03	Neck	Present 4.75 – 5.375 × 0.37 - 0.725	Like a constriction -	Present 1.904 – 2.004 × 0.219 - 0.357	Present 1.684 × 0.628
04	Testes	0.05-0.09 × 0.05 – 0.108 anterior to cirrus pouch	0.091 – 0.176 × 0.091 - 0.176 anterior to cirrus pouch	0.06 – 0.15 × 0.05 – 0.0685 Never near to anterior part of cirrus pouch	0.070 – 0.091 × 0.1 – 0.135 anterior to cirrus pouch
05	Cirrus pouch	0.17 - 0.525 × 0.23 - 0.4	0.774 - 0.529	0.21 - 0.25 × 0.134 - 0.197	0.384 × 0.384
06	External seminal vesicle	Present 0.04 – 0.06 × 0.04 - 0.08	Absent	Absent	Absent
07	Internal seminal vesicle	Absent	Absent	Present	Absent
08	Ovary	1.02 – 1.80 × 0.0675 - 1.32 U-shaped with even arms	4.19 – 4.65 × 1.37 U-shaped with uneven arms	1.12 – 1.89 × 0.199 – 0.315 U-shaped with even arms	2.742–2.914 × 1.2 – 1.3 U-shaped with even arms
09	Vitellaria	0.04 – 0.1 × 0.04 - 0.11	0.026 – 1.37 × 0.026 - 0.137	0.025 – 0.93 × 0.025 - 0.78	0.042 – 0.070 × 0.056 - 0.091
10	Receptaculum Seminis	Absent	Absent	Present	Absent
11	Genital Pore	Separate	Common	Separate	Common
12	Eggs Size Shape	0.026 - 0.036 × 0.026 - 0.038 Oval to round Non operculate	0.026 - 0.039 × 0.026 - 0.038 Spherical Non operculate	0.039 - 0.061 × 0.018 - 0.029 Elongated Non operculate	0.025 - 0.033 × 0.033 - 0.5 Oval to round operculate
13	Host	<i>Heteropneutes fossilis</i> (Bloch.)	<i>Mystusaor</i> (Ham.)	<i>Channa punctatus</i> (Bloch.)	<i>Heteropneutes fossilis</i> (Bloch.)
S.N.	Character	<i>Mystoides rajwaranesis</i>	<i>Mystoides bundelkhandensis</i>	<i>Mystoides Chhaviensis</i>	<i>Mystoidesragauliensis n.sp.</i>
01	Size	18.0 – 30.0 × 0.53-1.55	37.2 × 1.6	20.140×22.541× 0.864 – 0.964	34.0× 1.484
02	Scolex Size Shape	0.557 – 0.662 × 0.413- 0.45 Spoon like	1.60 × 0.57 Tube like without	0.565–0.812 × 0.208 – 0.279 Fimbricated with	0.970× 0.628 Thumb like without

Revised Key to species of genus *mystoides* of the family Capingentidae Hunter 1930

- 1 Postovarian median vitellaria present.....
- 2 Postovarian median vitellaria absent.....
- 6 Ovary U-shaped, uterin coils extending anterior to cirrus pouch
.....Sportoids Hunter 1929
- Ovary U-shaped, uterine coils not extending anterior to cirrus
pouch.....*Mystoides* Mathur 1992
- (i) Scolex tube like, neck like a constriction.....

.....Mystoides bundelkhandensis

(ii) Scolex spoon like, very long neck.....

.....Mystoides rajwaraensis.

(iii) Scolex Fimbriated with two grooves, medium neck.....

.....Mystoides chhaviensis

Scolex thumb like, short neck.....

.....Mystoides regauliensis. n.sp

Methodology

Materials and Methods :

The alimentary canal of the host was removed and cut open in normal saline water in Petridish, it was lightly shaken and the contents decanted several times. The intestine and its contents containing parasites were examined thoroughly under a binocular microscope. The worm was stretched in luke warm water and later fixed in 5% formalin.

The whole mount was stained in Mayer's Haemalum. Whole mount was cleared in xylol. Only camera lucida drawings were made. All the measurements were in millimeters unless other wise stated. These cestode was prepared for identification (Yamaguti 1959).

Observation

Mystoides ragauliensis n.sp. (Figs. 1-4)

Cestode large sized unsegmented measures 34.0 x1.484. Scolex smooth, blunt, well differentiated by a constriction without any cushion or groove measures 0.970 x0.628. Neck measures 1.684 x0.628.

Testes numerous medullary, oval to round measure 0.070 – 0.090 x0.1 - 0.135 (0.081 x0.121) anterior to cirrus pouch. Cirrus pouch oval, median measures 0.384 x0.384. Internal and external seminal vesicle absent.

Female genitalia posteriorly situated. Ovary U- shaped measures 2.742 – 2.914 x1.2-1.3 (2.8 x1.25) behind the cirrus pouch. Vitellaria partly cortical and partly medullary, preovarian, innumerable, oval to round measures 0.042–0.070 x 0.056–0.091(0.056 x 0.077) . Receptaculum seminis absent. Common genital atrium with male and female genital pore situated at the base of cirrus pouch.

Uterus long coiled tube, filled with numerous eggs extend up to the lower level of cirrus pouch. Eggs oval to round, operculate measure 0.025 - 0.032 x0.0332 - 0.05 (0.029 x0.04). Excretory tube measures 0.242 in length.

Result and Discussion

The present form comes closer to *Mystoides rajwaraensis*, *Mystoides bundelkhandensis* and *Mystoides chhaviensis* (Table-1)

The present form differs from *Mystoides rajwaraensis* in having larger worm, Thumb shaped wider scolex, short neck, larger testes, smaller cirrus pouch, absence of external seminal vesicle, larger ovary, larger vitellaria, oval operculate eggs and clear excretory tube.

The present form differs from *Mystoides bundelkhandensis* in having smaller worm, Thumb shaped wider scolex, clear neck, smaller testes, smaller cirrus pouch, smaller ovary with equal arms, smaller vitellaria, oval operculate eggs and longer excretory tube.

The present form differs from *Mystoides chhaviensis* in having larger worm, Thumb shaped wider scolex without groove, smaller neck, larger testes which anterior to cirrus pouch, larger cirrus pouch, absence of internal seminal vesicle, larger ovary, smaller vitellaria, absence of receptaculum seminis, common genital pore, oval operculate eggs and clear excretory tube.

In the light of above discussion it may be proposed to accommodate the present form as a new species *Mystoides ragauliensis* n.sp.

The species is named after the place from where it was collected.

Type species	-	<i>Mystoides ragauliensis</i> n.sp.
Host	-	<i>Heteropneustes fossilis</i> (Bloch.)
Habitat	-	Small intestine
Locality	-	Ragauli District Jalaun (U.P.) India
Number of specimen	-	01
Date of collection	-	25.04.2001
Deposition	-	Parasitological Labrotery Department of Zoology Bipin Bihari (P.G.) College, Jhansi (U.P.) India

Conclusion

New species of fish cestode is discovered and described with their morphology. This cestode parasite (*Mystoides ragauliensis*) can cause disease in fish and also pose risks to human health through consumption of infected fish.

References

1. Hunter G.W. (1930) *Studies on a Caryophyllaeidae of North America* 111 inois *Biological Monographs.* 11, 1-186
2. Hunter, G.W. III and Hunter, W.S. (1930) *Studies on the parasites of fishes of the lake champlain watershed Annu Rep. N.Y. state conservancy Dep. Biol Surv. Suppl.,* 197-216
3. Mathur N., Srivastav A.K. and Narayan Aditya (2014) *study of an unsegmented cestode from the fish Mystus aor from Bundelkhand region of Uttar Pradesh. Flora and Fauna* 20(2), 291-294.
4. Narayan Aditya and Singh Dharendra (2017) *Morpho-taxonomic study of an interesting cestode, Mystoides chhaviensis n.species of channa punctatus (Bloch.) from Parichha Dam District Jhansi Uttar Pradesh India. International Journal of Global Science Research Vol-4, Issue 2, October pp* 543-546.
5. Srivastav A.K., Singh A.R. and Narayan Aditya (2011) *Morphotaxonomic study of a new tape worm from edible fish Heteropneustes fossilis (Bloch.) from District Lalitpur (U.P.) India. Flora and Fauna* 17(1), 153-156
6. Yamaguti S. (1959) *Systema Helminthum, the cestodes of Vertebrates, Vol. 2, Interscience, New York, 1-860*